

Solvent Extraction Behaviour of Uranium with Liquid Cation—Exchanger(Versatic 10)**

UDAY SANKAR RAY* and SAGAR CHANDRA MODAK

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan, West Bengal, India

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The extraction of uranium from acetate solution with Versatic 10 in benzene was investigated. Uranium was quantitatively extracted at pH 5.6-5.8 from 0.1M acetic acid solution. The study included the effects of pH, extractant concentration, diluent, acetate ion concentration, ammonium sulphate concentration and contact time on the extraction of uranium. The probable composition of the extracted species was $UO_2R_2 \cdot 2HR$ (HR = Versatic 10). Uranium was separated from magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, manganese, cobalt, silver, cadmium, lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium, terbium, dysprosium, mercury, thallium, lead and thorium. Important quantitative separations of uranium from synthetic mixtures were also carried out.

INTEREST in the extraction of metal ions by commercial organic extractants has been indicated by several recent papers. Among the extractants acidic organophosphorus esters and carboxylic acids belong to liquid cation exchangers. Solvent extraction has been applied to the common metals owing to development of inexpensive extractants such as carboxylic acids. Recently the carboxylic acids such as Versatic acid and Naphthenic acid have become available in large quantities and at moderate prices as byproducts of petroleum industry and those carboxylic acids are used to study the extraction mechanism¹⁻⁴ and utilized in commercial plants⁵.

The typical carboxylic acids, Versatic 9, Versatic 911 and SRS-100 were used in this laboratory⁶⁻¹⁰ for the extraction of di-, tri- and tetravalent metals. The composition of the extracted species of several metals using Versatic 911 as extractant were investigated by several workers¹⁰⁻¹⁴.

No systematic attempt has yet been made to study the extraction behaviour of uranium with Versatic 10. This paper reports the extraction behaviour of uranium and determination of the composition of the extracted species using Versatic 10 in benzene as extractant. This offers a very simple and rapid method for extraction and separation of uranium at milligram level.

The extraction of metals by carboxylic acid occurs by a cation-exchange mechanism. In its simplest form the mechanism can be expressed by

Barred species are in the organic phase. While this equation is adequate for most practical purposes, it does not truly represent the extraction mechanism. Dimerization of the acid in an organic solvent or solvation of the extracted species by the carboxylic acid occurs in some cases. The carboxylic acid and the metal chelate formed have very little solubility in the aqueous solutions but are soluble in organic solvents.

It is evident from equation (1) that the extraction of metals by carboxylic acids is dependent on the pH of the aqueous phase. Use is made of this fact in the quantitative extraction and separation of metals by liquid-liquid extraction with Versatic 10.

Experimental

Apparatus :

Separatory funnels (250 ml) were used for extraction experiments. The pH measurements were carried out with an Elico pH meter (Elico, Model LI-10, Hyderabad, India).

Reagents :

Versatic 10, is a mixture of C_{10} isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acids¹⁵. It is manufactured and supplied by Shell Chemical Company, (London) and was used without further purification.

Uranyl acetate solution (1.047 mg/ml). About 2.1 gms of $UO_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ (BDH, AR) was dissolved in water. Uranyl acetate solution was obtained

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* To whom correspondence may be made.

by precipitation of the uranyl hydroxide and subsequent dissolution in one litre 0.2M acetic acid, and the solution was standardised by the complexometric titration with disodium ethylene diamine tetraacetate (EDTA) using xylenol orange indicator¹⁶.

Ascorbic acid (BDH, AR) was used for the reduction of U(VI) to U(IV) during the estimation of uranium.

The chemicals and solvents used were all of analytical grade unless otherwise mentioned.

General Extraction Procedure :

The procedure was based on solvent extraction technique. The ratio of the volumes of the aqueous phase and the organic phase was maintained at 2 : 1. The aqueous phase was made up from a portion of solution (10 ml) containing 10.47 mg of uranium in 0.2M acetic acid, sodium hydroxide was added to adjust pH. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 20 ml i.e., the ultimate concentration of uranium in the aqueous phase was $2.2 \times 10^{-3} M$. The solution was transferred into a separatory funnel and shaken with 10 ml of 33% Versatic 10 in benzene for 5 minutes. Contact time was varied from 0.5-10 minutes. Distribution ratio reached a constant value after 0.5 minute of shaking. Contact time of 5 minutes was used in all the experiments. The two layers were allowed to settle for 10 minutes. The aqueous phase was then separated and the equilibrium pH was measured. To remove organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the latter was washed with 5 ml of benzene. The resulting benzene extract was mixed with the separated organic phase. The amount of uranium present in the aqueous phase was estimated by EDTA titration. 20 ml of 2N nitric acid solution was added to the funnel and the mixture was shaken for 5 minutes. The two phases were allowed to settle and separate. The aqueous layer was carefully withdrawn and again washed with 5 ml of benzene to remove any entrained solvent present in the separated aqueous phase (acid extract). The amount of uranium extracted in that phase was estimated. Variations in procedure are indicated at appropriate places.

Results and Discussion

Effect of variables on the extraction :

pH : The extraction of uranium with Versatic 10 was performed at various pH, at constant acetate concentration (0.1M). With constant extractant concentration (33%) and constant metal concentration ($2.2 \times 10^{-3} M$), extraction of uranium increases with increased pH and becomes quantitative at pH 5.6-5.8. The distribution ratio (D) and the percentage extraction of uranium at different pH's are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—EXTRACTION OF URANIUM AS A FUNCTION OF pH

pH	Extraction of Uranium(%)	Distribution Ratio (D _u)
2.55	10	0.22
2.65	31.68	0.93
2.9	54.59	2.40
3.25	73.69	5.60
3.65	83.35	10.01
4.05	85.1	11.41
4.5	88.95	16.1
5.0	94.95	37.6
5.4	97.82	89.74
5.6	99.14	290.5
5.8	100.00	∞

Versatic 10 concentration :

The effect of extractant concentration on extraction was studied by varying the concentration of Versatic 10 from 0.2% to 33% using benzene as diluent. The extraction increased with increasing extractant concentration and was nearly complete at 33% Versatic 10. In the case of pure extractant, emulsion forming tendency increases with increased pH. To minimize this tendency all of the experiments have been carried out using 33% Versatic 10 in benzene.

Various diluents :

Uranium was extracted with Versatic 10 solution using carbon tetrachloride, benzene, xylene, toluene, chloroform, diisopropyl ether and nitrobenzene as diluents. The ratio of organic to aqueous phase was maintained at 1 : 2. Quantitative extraction of uranium was achieved in most of the cases. With the last two emulsion formation was noted.

Equilibration times : The contact time was varied from 30 secs to 10 min. The extraction was quantitative within 0.5 minute and back-extraction was complete within 1 minute. Contact time and stripping time was kept 5 minutes in all the experiments. 20 ml of 2N nitric acid was used for stripping uranium from the organic phase.

Ammonium sulphate concentration :

The effect of ammonium sulphate on the extraction was studied. Fig. 2 shows the dependency of extraction on ammonium sulphate concentration from 0.5M to 3M. Extraction of uranium is remarkably influenced by the presence of ammonium sulphate. At constant pH, with the increase of ammonium sulphate concentration in the aqueous phase, extraction decreases.

Acetate ion concentration :

The extraction dependence of uranium upon the acetate concentration showed that the extraction decreases with increase of acetate ion concentration.

Fig. 1. Extraction dependency of uranium on Versatic 10 concentration at pH 5.6.

Fig. 3. Acetate ion dependency on the extraction of uranium with Versatic 10.

Fig. 2. Extraction of uranium from $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ solutions with Versatic 10 (Versatic 10 : benzene = 1 : 2).

○-○-5M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, ◻-◻ 1M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$,
 ○-○-2M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, ◻-◻ 3M $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$.

The experiments were carried out at constant pH, constant metal ion concentration ($2.2 \times 10^{-8} M$) and constant extractant concentration (33%). In Fig. 3 it is shown that in all these conditions log D is proportional to $-\log [\text{Acetate}]$. The slope of logarithmic curve is -2.1 , indicating second power dependency of the extraction process on acetate ion concentration. This decrease in extraction is, perhaps, due to complexation of uranium with acetate ion.

Probable extraction mechanism :

The dependency of extraction of uranium on the extractant concentration is shown in Fig. 1. The extraction experiments were carried out at constant metal concentration ($2.2 \times 10^{-8} M$), constant acetate concentration (0.1M) and constant pH. Plot of log D against log [Versatic 10] produces a straight line with slope 1.93. Sanji *et al*¹¹ showed that Versatic acids exist as dimer in nonpolar solvents such as benzene. Taking into account this evidence, the extraction mechanism of uranium can be proposed.

where barred species are in the organic phase. R_2H_2 refers the dimeric form of Versatic 10 in benzene solution.

Extractive Separations :

The extractive separation procedure is very simple and rapid, requires in most of the cases only pH control. In some cases the interferences were removed by using suitable masking agents. Uranium (10 mg) was separated from magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, manganese, cobalt, cadmium, mercury, silver. The interferences due to lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium, terbium, dysprosium, thallium, lead and thorium was removed by using EDTA as masking agent. For those cases two consecutive extractions are required at the optimum

condition. EDTA does not interfere in the extraction process. Molybdate, vanadate, tungstate, oxalate, citrate and tartrate interfere in the extraction. The effect of diverse ions and their tolerance limits are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE EXTRACTION OF URANIUM(VI) WITH VERSATIC-10

Diverse ions	[Uranium, 10.5 mg. pH 5.8]		
	Amongt added	Source	Uranium extracted, %
Mg ²⁺	40 mg	MgSO ₄ , 7H ₂ O	100.00
Ca ²⁺	"	CaCl ₂ , 6H ₂ O	100.00
Sr ²⁺	"	SrCl ₂ , 6H ₂ O	100.00
Ba ²⁺	"	BaCl ₂ , 2H ₂ O	100.50
Mn ²⁺	10 mg	MnCl ₂ , 4H ₂ O	100.50
Co ²⁺	"	CoSO ₄ , 4H ₂ O	100.50
Ag ⁺	"	AgNO ₃	100.50
*La ³⁺	40 mg	La(NO ₃) ₃ , 6H ₂ O	101.00
*Th ⁴⁺	"	Th(NO ₃) ₄ , 6H ₂ O	101.00
*Ce ⁴⁺	"	Ce(SO ₄) ₂ , 4H ₂ O	102.00
*Pr ³⁺	"	Pr(NO ₃) ₃ , 6H ₂ O	101.00
*Nd ³⁺	"	Nd(NO ₃) ₃ , 6H ₂ O	102.00
*Sm ³⁺	"	Sm(NO ₃) ₃ , 6H ₂ O	99.50
*Dy ³⁺	"	Dy(NO ₃) ₃ , 6H ₂ O	101.00
*Cd ²⁺	"	Cd(NO ₃) ₂ , 6H ₂ O	102.00
*Tb ³⁺	"	Tb(NO ₃) ₃ , 6H ₂ O	101.00
Hg ²⁺	10 mg	HgCl ₂	100.00
*Tl ⁺	40 mg	Tl ₂ (SO ₄)	99.50
*Pb ²⁺	"	Pb(NO ₃) ₂	102.00
EDTA	"	EDTA (Disodium salt)	99.50

* EDTA was used as masking agent.

Separation of Uranium from Synthetic Mixtures. :

Uranium(VI) was separated quantitatively from synthetic mixtures like (1) U(VI) + Ag(I) + Mg(II) + Co(II), (2) U(VI) + Co(II) + Cd(II) + Hg(II), (3) U(VI) + La(III) + Tl(I) + Pb(II) + Th(IV) and (4) U(VI) + Co(IV) + Pr(III) + Nd(III) + Dy(III).

The synthetic mixtures were prepared by mixing 10 mg of each metal ions. In case of synthetic mixtures (3) and (4) EDTA was used as masking agent. The results are shown in the Table 3. In all the cases quantitative recovery of U(VI) was observed under the recommended extraction condition.

TABLE 3—QUANTITATIVE SEPARATION OF URANIUM(VI) FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES USING VERSATIC-10, (pH 5.8)

Sample No.	Mixture taken	Metal extracted, %
1.	U(VI) + Ag(I) + Mg(II) + Co(II)	100
2.	U(VI) + Co(II) + Cd(II) + Hg(II)	102
3.	U(VI) + La(III) + Tl(I) + Pb(II) + Th(IV)	102
4.	U(VI) + Co(IV) + Pr(III) + Nd(III) + Dy(III)	99.5

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References

1. A. W. FLETCHER and D. S. FLETT, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1964, **14**, 250.
2. L. M. GINDIN, *et al*, *Russ. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1960, **5**, 1146.
3. A. W. ASHBROOK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1721.
4. J. SHIBATA and S. NISHIMURA, *Trans. JIM*, 1977, **18**, 794.
5. D. S. FLETT, *Trans. Min. Metall.*, 1974, **83**, C90.
6. A. K. DE and U. S. RAY, *Sep. Sci.*, 1971, **6**, 25.
7. A. K. DE and U. S. RAY, *Sep. Sci.*, 1971, **6**, 443.
8. A. K. DE and U. S. RAY, *Sep. Sci.*, 1972, **7**, 409.
9. A. K. DE and U. S. RAY, *Sep. Sci.*, 1972, **7**, 419.
10. U. S. RAY and B. C. MODAK, *Sep. Sci. and Tech.* 1981, **16**, 87.
11. TATSUHIKO, SHIGEMATSU, SANJI, NISHIMURA, TERUO TANABE and YOSHIO, KONDO ; *Nippon Kinsoku Gakkaishi*, 1972, **36**, 445.
12. JUNJI, SHIBATA, MASAKARU, IZUTANI, HIROKI, KUWAHARA and SANJI, NISHIMURA ; *Nippon Kinsoku Gakkaishi*, 1974, **38**, 847.
13. JUNJI SHIBATA, and SANJI, NISHIMURA ; *Nippon Kinsoku Gakkaishi*, 1975, **39**, 206.
14. KOJI, KAZUOKA, TERUO, TANABE and YOSHIO, KONDO. *Nippon J. Kinsoku Gakkaishi*, 1975, **39**, 767.
15. H. GREEN, *Talanta*, 1973, **20**, 158.
16. RUDOLF. PRIBIL, *Chelometry, Basic Dterminations, Chemapol* (1961).